

Study on the Impact of Covid 19 Among Government School Going Adolescents in Perumbakkam- with Special Reference to Education

Nirmal.P, Dr. Prince Solomon Devadass, Johannes Samuel, Dr. Sudharsan

Abstract:- This study projects the study on the impact of the COVID 19 among the Government school going adolescent in Perumbakkam with special reference to the education. The COVID 19 has changed the way in which the people live, work or perform, their day to day activities. The main focus of the study is to study the demographic details of the government school going adolescent and to understand the implications of the online education among the adolescent and to understand the social factors affecting the adolescent in education, to analyze the physical and the mental challenges faced by the adolescent in reference to the online education and to identify the challenges in education during the pandemic. This study consists of the mixed methodology, for giving more importance to the quantitative followed by the qualitative data. The finding of the study is to understand all the factors affecting the adolescent during the online education. The aspects like the economic conditions during the online education have been identified and also the cognitive domains, psychological domain and also the challenges during the online education that also have been identified. This study entirely give the depth information about the education pattern which have been made an impact to the school going adolescent in all the aspects and also the challenges faced by the government school going adolescent.

Keywords:- COVID 19, Adolescent , Online Education, Physical and Mental Challenges.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence Education (AE) has been defined as an educational respond to adolescents' expressed in need of support, encouraging, clarifications, and information in order to make sense of their fast changing reality. The National Curriculum Framework (NCF) of 2005 recommends that education impart "independence of thought and action, sensitivity to others' well-being and feelings, learning to respond to new situations in a flexible and creative manner, predisposition toward participation in democratic processes, and the ability to work toward and contribute to economic processes and social change." AE's mission is to provide accurate, age-appropriate, and culturally relevant information to young people, as well as to promote healthy attitudes and develop skills that will enable them to respond to real-life circumstances. (Adolescence Education Programme (AEP), 2021) Girls and boys in adolescence (ages 10–19) continue to engage with the world in new ways, risk taking, gaining new abilities, and experiencing new emotions. They branch out

from their families to create strong bonds with their peers. They look for ways to stand out and belong, to find their position in society and to make a difference. This current generation of young people is larger than any other in history. However, far too many people are not receiving the support they require to fully exercise their rights. Poverty and deprivation, gender inequality, as well as other forms of discrimination combine with climate change, economic instability, violence, and displacement to pose a threat to the well-being of adolescents. Adolescents are all too often overlooked by officials, or worse, seen as problems or threats.

Students demand more independence and intellectual independence as they move in school. They can use online learning to undertake highly individual learning programmes, involving college-level courses. These, especially paired with hands-on exercises, direct experience, and thorough assessments, can help them learn more effectively. Before committing to a specialty, they might explore their options by trying out introductory topics from several fields. Before they enter college, virtual education platforms can assist these kids in becoming more independent learners. I feel that rather than discouraging students from taking an online course, we should help them navigate through it.

The sudden shift to online education to fight the COVID-19 pandemic has dramatically changed the lives of adolescents all across the world. The goal of this study is to identify psychological characteristics that are related with adolescents' well-being in terms of positive emotion and intrinsic learning motivation, as well as key characteristics of their learning behaviour in an unplanned, involuntary distance education circumstance. Experienced competence, autonomy, and relatedness were assumed to positively relate to active learning behaviour (i.e., engagement and persistence) and negatively relate to passive learning behaviour (i.e., procrastination), mediated by positive emotion and intrinsic learning motivation, according to Self-Determination Theory. Data was collected using online questionnaires in eight countries across Europe, Asia, and North America (N = 25,305), with results predicted to be comparable across nations. Expertise was consistently demonstrated. found to relate to positive emotion and intrinsic learning motivation, and, in turn, active learning behaviour in terms of engagement and persistence. The study results further highlight the role of perceived relatedness for positive emotion. The high proportions of explained variance speak in favour of taking these central results into account when designing distance education in times of COVID-19.

The resettlement colonies themselves have come under criticism for their lack of basic civic amenities, the condition of the houses and the absence of proper transport, education and health facilities available for residents here. These shortfalls have been exacerbated by the pandemic and the resultant lockdown. Old TNSCB tenements in Tsunami Nagar are a mere 120 sq.ft. The newer tenements in Perumbakkam measure 380 sq ft. The lockdown and COVID-related isolation has seen entire families share such a small, stifling space for months. “My family of five has had a tough time. The single living room that we all share felt more like a prison when everyone was forced to be home all the time. The past few months have been worrisome because we share Common toilets and water has also been an issue. So far, we have luckily not seen many cases in our block but the lockdown was extremely difficult to manage,” says Semmalar T of Kannagi Nagar. The small size of the tenements made isolation for those infected with COVID-19 a stressful experience. Dr Archana Padmakar, Deputy Director at The Banyan, working on mental health with poor and vulnerable communities, says, “We have families which access our outpatient clinics, who have had relatives diagnosed with COVID-19. They hardly have space to isolate themselves, as they have only one room in some cases.”

Those affected by COVID-19 had the option of being isolated at the government-run COVID Care Centres. But many of them were discharged in a week. Upon their return, they had to remain isolated in their homes, which proved to be a big challenge given the size of these dwellings. Dr Archana points out that some of them isolated themselves along with their family and avoided stepping out, in view of public health concerns. In some other cases neighbours took the responsibility of the children, while some sent other family members away to relatives' houses. (Natarajan, COVID proved to be a greater challenge in Chennai's resettlement colonies, 2020)

Approximately 38% of which put a financial burden on them. Gupta, however, advocated a two-way interaction between teachers and students and emphasised on holding practical classes. “Over 50% of the schools share one way pre-recorded or live videos to conduct online classes,” he added. Also, at least 83% of the respondent parents supervised their children's studies and home tasks during the lockdown and 66% of the students did self-study at home. While 92% of the respondent parents gave consent to the schools to hold online classes. Mobile phones emerged as the most preferred medium for virtual teaching, which was between one and eight hours a day. There have been some positive spin-offs of online classes for the children, including a greater focus on self-study and value for time, exploring new technological tools, and showing greater affection to their family members. (Rawal, 2020)

II. METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is vital of any research as it enables the research in searching the result for the problem studied. It is important to use appropriate methodology while doing the research. This chapter comprises of methodologies such as objectives of the study, the tools used for data collection, research design, conceptual and operational definition key words.

➤ *Objective*

1. To study the demographic details of the respondents
2. To identify the implications of the online education among the adolescents
3. To understand the social factors affecting the adolescents in education
4. To analyze the physical and mental challenges faced by the adolescents in reference to the education.
5. To identify the challenges in education during the pandemic

➤ *Universe*

Universe of the study is the total group of people where the study is carried out. The universe of the study is school going adolescent from the age group of (15 to 17) years studying in the Perumbakkam Government Higher Secondary School.

➤ *Inclusion Criteria*

Inclusive criteria are the characteristics that the prospective subjects must have if they are to be included in the study. The inclusion criteria are the sample are

1. The respondent should be a adolescent from the age group of (15-17) years of age
2. The respondent should be a higher secondary student of Government Higher Secondary school Perumbakkam

➤ *Sample Size*

The sample size for the Quantitative study is 60 Respondents

The sample size for the Qualitative study is 8 Respondents

➤ *Tools For Data Collection*

● *For Quantitative*

For collecting the quantitative data the researcher used the Self structured questionnaire for collecting the quantitative data

● *For Qualitative*

For collecting the qualitative data the researcher used an In Depth Interview Guide

III. RESEARCH RESULTS

➤ *Occurrence of technical issues*

Occurrence	No of Respondent	Percent (%)
Has issues Regularly	58	96.7
Has issues Sometimes	2	3.3
Total	60	100.0

Occurrence of technical issues, absolute majority (97%) of the respondent has issues Regularly, considerable proportion (3%) of the respondent has issues Sometimes occurrences technical issues

➤ *Stress on Affective domain*

Score	Stress Level	No of Respondent	Percent (%)
0 -31	Low	5	9
32-62	Moderate	49	81
63 -93	High	6	10
94 -124	Very High	0	0
Total		60	100

Stress on affective domain, high majority (81%) of the respondents had moderate stress level in the affective domain , considerable proportion (10%) of the respondent had high level in the affective domain, considerable proportion (9%) of the respondent had low stress level in the affective domain, None of the respondent had the very high level in the affective domain

➤ *Syllabus and portion have been covered*

Syllabus and portion	No of Respondent	Percent (%)
Full Coverage	12	20.0
Mid coverage	28	46.7
Not covered	20	33.3
Total	60	100.0

Show the percentage of syllabus and portion covered, half of the respondent((47%) half of the respondent says the portion have been covered only to the midterm , considerable proportion (20%) of the respondent says the portion have been covered fully, , one third (33%) of the respondent says the portion have been covered fully during the online education

➤ *Comfortable in attending the online in home*

Comfortable	No of Respondent	Percent (%)
Comfortable	35	58.3
Uncomfortable	22	36.7
Discomfort	3	5.0
Total	60	100.0

Show the percentage of the comfortable in attending in home, less than one third (58%) of the respondent says comfortable, less than half (36%) of the respondent says uncomfortable, considerable proportion (5%) of the respondent says discomfort for attending the online class in home

IV. DISCUSSION ON THE MAIN FINDINGS

From the data collected , 65% of the respondents belong to the age group of 16 this age is considered is as the middle stage of the adolescent period. The majority of the participated in the research is the age of 16 that is studying in the 11th standard so the researcher gave importance to the middle stage of the adolescent group to get participated in the research.

While considering the family details of the participant 86.7% of the participant’s parents are married and together,. The majority of the participants parents are staying together and they all belong to the nuclear family, all the families in the resettlement areas have been resettled from one place to the another.

According to the data collected Preferred device for the online is 87% of the respondent use the mobile phone, most of the parents of the respondent are the daily wages worker and due to the pandemic sometimes they cannot able to go for work, so they can able to afford only the smart phone for attending the online classes.

While considering the source of the internet 93.3% of the respondent use the mobile network (data pack), the majority is the 93.3% of the respondent have used the mobile data for the online education in view of the according to the data from the department of education states that majority of the people are using the mobile internet. (education) 90% of the respondent have been faced the lack of device during the online class. The majority of this, is that the respondents have been attending the online class from the parents phone so if they go for the employment the mobile won’t be available for the participant to attend the online class from home during the pandemic.

According to the data 45% of the respondents are comfortable with the home peer groups while attending the online class, 53% of the respondents are uncomfortable with the home peer groups while attending the online class and 2% of the respondents sometimes they will feel comfortable with the home peer groups while attending the online classes Family income reliable for the family to afford device for the respondent, 73% of the respondent family income was unaffordable for getting the device for the online education, and 27% of the respondent family income is reliable to afford device for the respondent to attend the online class, due to the migration and the unemployment the families income is nit reliable to afford device for the respondent to attend the online class.

According to the data, the 83% of the respondents are moderate in the cognitive domain and 17% of the respondents are high in the stress on the cognitive domain, the cognitive domain consists of the regular activities of the day like the working control and the other aspect. Stress on the behavioural domain 81% of the respondent was moderate, 17% of the Respondents are low in the behavioural domain, and 17% of the respondents are high in the behavioural domain. And stress on the affective domain 81% of the respondent are low, 10% of the respondent are the high and 9% of the respondent are the low in the affective domain. Stress on the physiological domain 66% of the respondents is moderate and 34% of the respondents are high in the physiological domain.

V. CONCLUSION

“Education is a right to everyone, so all the citizens in the society should get the education” The education is the one of the important for all and it should not be denied by any view of cause. The education whether it might be an online or offline it should reach the people who are in all the areas. In view of the online education it should be much strengthened in the resettlement area, rural areas and also in the tribal areas. The education will make a change in one self and also in the society.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

Government should build the Resettlement tenement in the feasibility of the network towers in the areas. The respected authority Tamil Nadu Urban Habitat Development Board, should check the feasibility of the network towers in the area, otherwise the network towers have to be included in the resettlement area, the Perumbakam consists of 5 schools inside the scheme, so in view of this the network towers have to be implemented in the area for the students future online education The education department should focus more on the resettlement areas for the education system during the pandemic, due to the lack of amenities for the online education the standard of the education system is getting low in the resettlement areas. And also the Tamil Nadu educational department should bring up schemes for the students regarding the mobile phones and the scheme should be benefitted by the all the government school students.

The NGO's in the Perumbakkam resettlement scheme should take the initiative in providing the needed amenities for the students during the online education, like providing the Gadgets and also the feasibility of the network connection or the Wi-Fi connections for the school going students.

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